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Reciprocal control of IL-32 and IL-33 by TNFa.

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We describe here previously unappreciated reciprocal control of IL-32 and IL-33 by TNFa.

Citations

1. Nold-Petry, C.A., Nold, M.F., Zepp, J.A., Kim, S.H., Voelkel, N.F. and Dinarello, C.A., 2009. IL-32–dependent effects of IL-1 β on endothelial cell functions. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 106(10), pp.3883-3888.